

ISic1392

I.Sicily inscription 1392

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

basalt (?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Aetna

Place of origin (modern)

Santa Maria di Licodia

Provenance

S.Maria di Licodia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Santa Maria di Licodia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140899

1. Ἡ [ρό] δω[ρ]ος
2. χρηστὸς ἔζησε
3. [ἔτ]η Γ[— —]ΓΙΑΚΕ Φ
4. [— — — — —]ΛΙ#⁷A
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493007

EDCS 39101519

PHI 140899

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0573 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5734

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